

pflA Complementation

Supplementary Figure S5. Complementation growth curve of $\Delta pflA$ in M9 0.5% glucose 50mM fumarate media grown anaerobically. $\Delta pflA$ strain was complemented with IPTG-inducible vector pMB66EH. WT and $\Delta pflA$ strains were induced with 1mM IPTG. (+) indicates the addition of IPTG inducer whereas (-) indicates the lack thereof. 'pe' denotes an empty vector control whereas 'pA' indicates the complementation plasmid contains the *pflA* open reading frame. Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.